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NUMERICAL ANALYSIS OF CIRCULAR NOTCHED CONNECTIONS ON CLT AND CONCRETE COMPOSITE PLATES

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ABSTRACT:

CLT-concrete composite plates, with a concrete layer on the upper surface, have optimized structural performance for flexural stiffness, dynamics, as well as, a better thermal, acoustic, and behavior against fire situation than CLT plates. Different kinds of timber and concrete connections have been studied for many years for unidirectional structural elements such as beams and for different applications. For CLT-concrete plates, a bidirectional analysis is required considering the two orthogonal directions of the plate. In this paper, circular notched connections are studied for the two orthogonal directions of CLT-concrete plates. Thicker internal layers for CLT are used in order to homogenize the strength and stiffness in both orthogonal directions of the plate for a biaxial load transfer instead of a uniaxial load transfer as they are generally used. A numerical analysis of the push-out tests of two different specimens simulating the connections in the orthogonal directions of CLT-concrete plates was performed for determining the stiffness and the slip modulus. The results showed that the values of the slip modulus were different for both longitudinal and transversal directions, that the notch depth has an influence on the slip modulus and that the circular geometry of the notch can be an interesting alternative for the two-way CLT-concrete plates.

KEYWORDS: CLT-concrete composite plates, circular timber notches, push-out tests, bi-directional analysis, FEM

1 INTRODUCTION

The composite slabs made of CLT and concrete bring advantages in structural performance, for flexural stiffness, dynamics, thermal, acoustic, and behavior against fire situation comparing to timber plates [1].

Common solutions for connections between timber and concrete are screws, notches, steel plates, glued connections etc. [2], [3], [4]. The connections between CLT and concrete plates can be the same as for timber-concrete composite beams, however, they should be analyzed in a two-way spanning system instead of unidirectionally.

Considering a one-way spanning system, and uniaxial load transfer, CLT and concrete beams connected with structural adhesive and notches in wood were tested in [1] and adhesive provided less relative displacement than the connection by notches, as expected according to [3]. In [5] four different types of connections for CLT and concrete were studied: screws inclined at 45° next to each other, more spaced screws, HBV connection (steel mesh reinforcement, [6]) and shear bolts with steel

plates. The inclined screws developed a partial interaction between wood and concrete and HBV type [6], had the highest load capacity.

Mechanical connections between concrete and timber for a plate structural solution are still missing, both for GLC (Glued Laminated Timber), CLT and concrete, or even for other wood engineering products.

Considering the composite CLT and concrete working in a plate-like behavior, the authors in [7] studied CLT-concrete plates with two types of connections: continuous rectangular notches and inclined screws following the principal stresses path in the plate.

The novelty of the present work is the study of the stiffness of circular notches manufactured in the CLT plates for connecting with the concrete, based on the work developed by [7], who studied continuous rectangular notches orthogonally distributed in the CLT-concrete plate. Circular notch connections were chosen because, as an advantage with respect to continuous notches, they can be distributed through the most stressed areas of the plate specifically and can be manufactured with a numerical control machine during the CLT manufacturing process, in addition to the notch stiffness [4], [5], [6].

The aim of the present work is to estimate the stiffness and the slip modulus of circular notched connections between CLT and concrete by numerical simulation of the push-out tests in the two orthogonal directions of the

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CLT-concrete mixed plates, in addition to assessing the normal stress distribution on the simulated-specimens.

2 METODOLOGY

2.1 CLT-CONCRETE SLAB

A two-way spanning CLT-concrete composite slab was investigated in determining the biaxial load-bearing behavior of the connection system.

CLT-concrete plates of $2400 \times 2400 \text{ mm}^2$ were designed, with an upper concrete layer of 40 mm of thickness, and 5-layers CLT with a total thickness of 160 mm.

The main objective in the design of the CLT-concrete plates was to homogenize the strength and stiffness in both orthogonal directions for a biaxial load transfer instead of a uniaxial. For this purpose, thicker internal layers were used for CLT, as showed in the composite notched plate according to Figure 1.

Figure 1: CLT-concrete circular notched plate, circular notch view in direction i) and in direction ii). Dimensions in mm.

Connecting concrete and CLT with notches, both parts of the composite must resist the shear flow and both CLT layers, in 0° and 90° directions contributing to the shear stiffness and strength.

2.2 NOTCHES IN CLT

Circular notches of 140 mm of diameter, showed in figure 1, were studied in a two-way span system following the recommendations of [8], which summarized load-bearing behavior of notches in a one-way spanning system. According to [8] the depth of the notches in the wood, varies from 10mm to 50mm and the distance between notches vary from 150 to 400mm and the length of the notch is between 100mm to 300mm and the angle of the lateral face is 90° , as it was found that there was no increase in stiffness for other angles. To design the notch depth and length the work of [9] was also taken into account.

Regarding the depth of the notches: i) the notch depth should reach the second layer of the CLT panel when the first layer is perpendicular to the shear load in order to improve their shear stiffness; ii) when the first layer is parallel to the grain, the notch depth should not be in the interface of the layers because it can cause a worse rolling shear effect in the second layer, resulting in a depth of 40 mm, shown in figure 2.

2.3 PUSH-OUT TESTS

To evaluate the mechanical behavior, strength and rigidity (slipping modulus), of the connection between concrete and wood [10] standard is currently applied. [10] specifies loading cycles and test equipment, however, it does not standardize the specimen dimensions and test geometry. Although there is no standard method to evaluate wood concrete shear connector properties, several authors have conducted shear tests in a variety of configurations for the push-out test, [11],[12].

In this study, a symmetric configuration has been adopted with the concrete in the interior of the specimen as shown in figure 2 and CLT in the exterior. This configuration was chosen based on the simplicity of manufacturing the specimen, considering the CLT as formwork. Also, if CLT was on the interior side of the composition, there would be two shear planes, which would mean that, the wood-part had to be sufficiently thick to avoid any possible interference between connectors on the other side.

The push-out specimens were also designed considering a distance in front of the notch of 190 mm attending the recommendations of [8], according to figure 2.

2.4 NUMERICAL MODEL

A numerical model of the push-out tests was developed in ANSYS Workbench software, as it is shown in Figure 2. Two different specimens were designed to simulate the connections in the two orthogonal directions of the CLT-concrete composite plates aiming to estimate the

slip modulus (k_{ser}): i) 20L-30T-20L-30T-20L, made by longitudinal layers of 20 mm of thickness and transversal layers of 30 mm of thickness; and ii) 20T-30L-20T-30L-20T, made by 20 mm and 30 mm of thickness for transversal and longitudinal layers, respectively. For exterior layers C30 strength class was used C20 strength class for the internal ones, from Vilela [13], according to [14]. The nonlinear mechanical properties of used concrete were of $f_{ck} = 30$ MPa (Compressive strength), $E_c = 26$ GPa (Elastic modulus) and $\nu = 0,2$ (Poisson's ratio).

Figure 2: CLT-concrete push-out test specimen. Dimensions in mm.

In the finite element model, showed in figure 3, solid elements named SOLID186 were chosen to incorporate material orthotropies and to simulate the interface

between timber and concrete and for their relative displacement, contact elements were used, CONTA174, TARGE170 and SURF154. The mesh was discretized in a total of 37680 nodes, and 6766 elements and the maximum dimension of the elements were 10 mm.

Figure 3: Numerical model of the push out test of CLT-concrete plate in solid elements.

Doble symmetry was imposed in the numerical model and the boundary conditions are illustrated in figure 4. The load was applied in the upper surface of the concrete and the inferior support in CLT restricted vertical displacements and cylindrical support was used to restrict lateral displacement of timber.

Figure 4: Boundary conditions of the problem

CLT and concrete layers were created in parts and linked by contact properties. Bonded contacts were attributed between CLT layers contact region and frictionless were set in the interface between CLT-concrete and CLT-roller (cylindrical support).

The slip modulus K_{ser} (kN/mm) was estimated, according to [9], considering the maximum Force (F_{max}) related to a displacement of 15 mm and in the region of 10% and 40% of the maximum load, F_{max} , from the load-displacement curve.

3 RESULTS

3.1 SLIP MODULUS WITH CIRCULAR NOTCHES WITH DEPTH OF 40 mm

Figure 5 presents the load-displacement graphic of the push-out test of CLT-concrete plates connected by circular notches—with 40 mm of diameter and in the two orthogonal directions.

From the results obtained the slip modulus (K_{ser}) for the plate direction, where shear force was perpendicular to the grain (ii direction – curve A2), was approximately 88 kN/mm, while in the other direction (i direction – curve A1) was approximately 72 kN/mm, according to Figure 5 and in the service range shown in Figure 6.

Figure 5: Slip Modulus for notches of 40 and 15 mm of depth in the two directions of CLT-concrete plate, longitudinal and transversal.

Comparing the results obtained in curve A1, exhibited in figure 5, with the results in [8], for solid wood and GLT, for the shear force parallel to the grain direction in the continuous notch, the values were smaller for circular notches. Continuous notch connection slip modulus, K_{ser} , varied from 800 to 1800kN/mm/m for a meter wise, while for circular notched obtained value for a meter wise was approximately 500 kN/mm/m.

In the work of [7], the slipping modulus, K_{ser} obtained in the push out tests for both directions in CLT-concrete plate connected by continuous notches of 200 mm length and 20 mm depth, varied considerably considering the direction of the grain in the notch region, and was approximately 600 kN/mm/m for the plate direction

where shear force was parallel to the grain (i direction) and was 100 kN/mm/m for shear force perpendicular to the grain (ii direction). These values are both different to the ones obtained in the numerical model. Moreover, the results for K_{ser} shown in figure 5, contrasted with the ones obtained in [7] where K_{ser} in the principal direction was 6 times higher than in the weaker direction of CLT-concrete plate.

Figure 6: Service range for calculating slip modulus for notches of 40 and 15 mm in the CLT-concrete plate, longitudinal and transversal.

3.2 SLIP MODULUS WITH CIRCULAR NOTCHES WITH DEPTH OF 15 mm

In order to have less depth notches and also verify whether [7] recommendations were valid, and to compare with values of [8], 15 mm notches were simulated. The curves A3 and A4 were obtained according to Figure 5 and Figure 6, with a smaller stiffness comparing to the 40mm notches as expected and with the higher slip modulus for direction ii (curve A3).

The values for both directions (A3 and A4) were very close, like for 40 mm notches. These similar values in both directions contribute to the homogenization of the plate in the orthogonal directions.

The recommendation in [7] that the notch should reach the longitudinal layer to improve the stiffness is not valid for circular notches and the results contrasted with the ones obtained in [7], where K_{ser} in the principal direction was 6 times higher than in the weaker direction of CLT-concrete plate. Due to notch geometry, there is a contribution in resistance and stiffness in the longitudinal and transversal directions.

In addition, horizontal deformation around the circular notches were noticed due to their geometry and because there was no restriction in the displacement of the notch.

Associating it in the composite plate there will be opposite reactions between notches.

3.3 NORMAL STRESS

When analyzing the normal stress acting on the numerically simulated CLT-concrete specimens, a significant difference in the stress distribution both in the concrete and in the CLT for the different specimens evaluated in this study was observed. Figure 7 exhibits the distribution of normal stresses in the y-direction along the longitudinal-section of the specimens for a force of approximately 51 kN.

Figure 7: Normal stress in y-axis direction for $F \cong 51$ kN.

From the results obtained, it appears that the highest normal compression stresses tend to be inversely proportional to the depth of the notch. Since, in specimens with external layers with fibers transverse to the force, the normal stresses were greater than those observed in their pairs. In general, the path of normal efforts in the CLT was limited to the layers permeated by the notch, with the exception of the A1 specimen. In this case, the external layer in contact with the notch has a considerably greater modulus of elasticity than the layer

immediately below in the direction evaluated, depending on the strength class and grain direction.

In all the simulated models, the region with the highest concentration of tension in the concrete was the same, however, the intensity of this stress changed according to the model. From this observation, it is pertinent for the use of CLT-concrete slabs to provide reinforcement on the underside of the concrete in this region above the notch in order to increase the resistance capacity of the structure.

It is worth mentioning that the present study is part of a PhD thesis and as a future research, experimental push-out tests will be carried out to validate the numerical modelling and determined the notch stiffness and their strength with a great accuracy too. Figure 8 displays the CLT-concrete specimen preparation for the future push out tests.

CLT part of the specimen

Formwork lateral view

Formwork superior view

Figure 8: CLT-concrete specimen preparation for push out tests.

4 CONCLUSIONS

From the study of the composite CLT-concrete plate with circular notches, it was noticed that the notch depth has an influence on the slip modulus and stress distributions. It was also noted that the highest normal compression stresses tend to be inversely proportional to the depth of the notch.

The results showed that because of the circular geometry of the notch it is not necessary to reach the CLT longitudinal layer to improve their stiffness. In addition, due to their geometry, horizontal deformation in the notches were noticed and because there was no displacement restriction for the notch, in the composite plate there will be opposite reactions between notches. So circular notches can be an interesting alternative for application in the two-way CLT-concrete plates.

As a future part of the research, an experimental tests should be performed in order to validate the numerical model.

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